

Reconsidering the Emergence and Dynamics of Siamese City-states During the Early and the Age of Commerce (13th-15th centuries) Along the Trans-Peninsula Trade Routes

Abstract

This article synthesizes and re-evaluates historical interpretations regarding the dynamics and expansion of the population groups identified in external sources as “**Siam**,” “**Syam**,” or “**Xian**” (暹). Commonly associated with Tai-Kadai-speaking communities of the Chao Phraya basin and the Malay Peninsula, these groups began to appear with increasing clarity and prominence in Chinese records from the thirteenth century onward. Evidence indicates extensive patterns of dispersion across key nodes of regional trade routes. These communities gradually consolidated at critical logistical intersections—ranging from overland caravan tracks and mountain pass to riverine networks connecting hinterland resource zones with coastal port cities along the Gulf of Martaban and the Gulf of Thailand.

This phenomenon occurred during the critical transition from the “**Early Age of Commerce**” (**Geoff Wade**) to the height of the “**Age of Commerce**” (**Anthony Reid**). Drawing on **Kenneth R. Hall**’s framework of maritime trade-driven statecraft, this study argues that the formation of early Tai-Siamese polities was defined by networks of “port-polities” and commercial hubs (**Mueang/Nakhon**).

Through a comparative analysis of primary epigraphic evidence and chronicle sources alongside the Chinese annals and maritime records, this study synchronizes local narratives with global commercial trends. The findings suggest that the emergence of these states was intrinsically linked to the logistics of trans-peninsula trade routes. Ultimately, this reconsideration offers a nuanced perspective on how early Siamese statecraft was shaped by the mobilization of hinterland resources and manpower, effectively serving as a vital bridge between the Indian Ocean and the Far East, and integrating these emerging polities into the core of the pre-modern global maritime network.

Keywords: Thai Historiography, Age of Commerce, Port-polities, 13th-15th Centuries Southeast Asia, Tai polities, Siamese city-states, Sukhothai, Ayutthaya, Age of commerce, Xian (Siam), Luohu (Lavo)

Introduction

Before the historical appearance of the term “Siam” (Syām, Syangka, Xian), the Dvaravati cultural sphere in the Chao Phraya basin had gradually declined and was subject to varying degrees of Angkorian influence. From the late 10th century, authority emanating from the Tonle Sap region intermittently extended westward through Lavo (Lavapura), a strategic node linking the Khorat Plateau and the Gulf of Thailand. Fluctuations in this control are reflected

in the O-Samet inscription (K.1198), which refers to instability in Lavapura before renewed Angkorian consolidation.¹

A significant shift in the historical record appeared in the 12th century during the reign of Suryavarman II, whose temple complex, Angkor Wat, preserves in its southern gallery the inscriptional reference to “Neh Syam Kuk.” This is generally regarded as the earliest secure epigraphic attestation of the term “Syam” as a collective designation associated with groups connected to Lavo in the Chao Phraya basin. Subsequent references to related terms—such as “Syangka” in the Old Javanese *Deśawarnana* and “Xian” (暹) in Chinese records—appear with increasing frequency from the 13th century onward. This development aligns with the widespread expansion of Tai-speaking groups and the rise of powerful new Tai states across the central mainland; a phenomenon so pronounced since the 13th century that David K. Wyatt characterized it as ‘A Tai Century.’

Previous scholarship has often remained limited in depth, often lacking a rigorous and contemporary analysis of both local and Chinese primary sources. Furthermore, interpretations framed within Global History frequently overlook the nuanced Southeast and East Asian worldviews of the period. Such perspectival gaps can lead to interpretations that are disconnected from their authentic historical contexts. Addressing these deficiencies, this study integrates contemporary analyses of local sources with established theoretical frameworks on Southeast Asian state formation.

Post-Angkorian Dynamics in the Chao Phraya Basin and the Malay Peninsula

The 13th Century as a Period of Regional Transition

The 13th to early 14th centuries are widely regarded as a pivotal transitional era in Southeast Asia.²

Following the expansive logistical and political integration initiated under Jayavarman VII, large-scale networks radiating from the Tonle Sap extended across the Dangrek range into the Khorat Plateau—most notably to Phimai—and westward toward the Chao Phraya basin at the end of the 12th century control over one of the largest hydrographic systems of mainland Southeast Asia.³ However, as argued by Lustig (2009), the Angkorian system shows little archaeological evidence of coinage circulation, suggesting limited monetary integration. Thus, these networks likely functioned primarily for the extraction of raw materials rather than for monetized commercial exchange.

After the decline of ambitious centralized Angkorian oversight in the mid-13th century, previously subordinated local power bases began to reorganize their own political and commercial networks with increasing autonomy. A significant indicator of this shift is the

¹ See Kmonrat (2021: 108)

² Marked by the collapse of classical power structures such as Pagan and Angkor on the mainland, alongside the waning influence of the Srivijaya maritime empire in the peninsula. See Lieberman (2003)

³ See Miltzer o’Naghten (2014: 408)

embassy sent on 9 December 1289, by Lavo (羅斛) to the Yuan court, together with “Nüren Guo” (女人國), commonly identified with Haripuñjaya.⁴ (YS 15: 15a) This mission may indicate Lavo's renewed participation in China-oriented diplomatic exchanges after centuries within the Angkorian political orbit.

The joint mission with Haripuñjaya—two centers historically linked since the Dvaravati period— may reflect the reactivation of older regional connections following the weakening of external domination.

They point to a broader regional process in which inland polities began redirecting their orientation toward maritime outlets.

Reassessing Chao Phraya Basin Dynamics: Trade, Autonomy, and Open Corridors

14th century inscriptions that recount events of the early 13th century provide additional insight into this transitional phase. The Wat Sri Chum inscription of Sukhothai, for example, reveals patterns of shifting alliances, military confrontation, and the reconfiguration of authority in the Upper Chao Phraya basin.

Moreover, this inscription and face 2 of the Wat Khao Kop inscription also detail the 14th-century transportation and pilgrimage routes from a city-state in the upper basin through Mon port and the Bay of Bengal to South India and Sri Lanka.

By the early-to-mid-14th century, clearer patterns emerge of interconnected communities situated along river routes, overland caravan passages, and coastal ports. **[Map 1]** Mobility intensified due to trade, warfare, religious missions, and pilgrimage movements stretching from the Malay Peninsula to interior zones such as Lanna and Yunnan.

The well-known passage from the Ramkhamhaeng inscription—“Whoever wishes to trade in elephants trades; whoever wishes to trade in horses trades; whoever wishes to trade in silver and gold trades”—portrays an image of a relatively open trade society across borders. Whether fully literal or ideologically constructed, this statement aligns with Sukhothai's strategic location that located along trade routes between the Gulf of Martaban and the central Mekong River basin (Singtuen et al. 2024: 2). This strategic position may also have facilitated the wider circulation of new metallic currencies like “Pod Duang” (also known as Bullet coin), that appears to have a high silver purity for 97% to 99% (Krisdaolarn 2016: 94-117), and new zinc coins called “Pod Duang Chin” or “Ngern Kub,” which may used both as currency and for weight (Niyom 2558), initiated in this regions, and spread through its trading network along the Chao Phraya basin and neighboring regions such as Lanna.

The event of diplomatic missions from Haripuñjaya and Lavo towards China in 1289, while Sukhothai consistently occupied a territory along transportation routes between these two

⁴ Modern scholarship has often associated 女人國/女王國 with Haripuñjaya; See Cheng Shu-Fang (鄭淑方) (2020: 12)

cities may suggest that in this era the riverine and overland routes have retained characteristics of relatively open resource corridors rather than rigid territorial monopolies.

Map 1: Mid-14th century Trans-Peninsula Hubs & Transportation Routes Drawing by the Author

The configuration of power on the Malay Peninsula in the Late 13th Century

In the southern peninsula, developments centered on Nakhon Si Thammarat (Tambralinga). After the second invasion of Sri Lanka in 1262 by King Chandrabhanu—who was ultimately defeated by Jatavarman Vira Pandyan of the Pandyan dynasty (Sinha & Banerjee 1947: 199)—the polity may have experienced a temporary disruption of rulership. This coincided chronologically with the early reign of King Ramkhamhaeng from the Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai polity, whose Sukhothai inscriptions and Lanna religious chronicles such as *Sihinganiḍāna* (1404-1446) and *Jinakālamāli* (1527) indicate the close religious' connections with Nakhon Si Thammarat during his reign.

According to the Nakhon Si Thammarat chronicles, in 1273 a ruler named Sri Sai Narong (ศรีไสยณรงค์) arrived from the west (which, likely implied the north) to assume authority. (TMNST: 181) The name corresponds to the King of Sukhothai named Sai Narong who brought the Pra Phutta Sihing image from Nakorn Si Thammarat to Sukhothai in *Sihinganiḍāna* and a royal figure listed in Sukhothai genealogies—Sai (...) Songkhram (ไส...สงคราม)⁵, following Ramkhamhaeng in the Sukhothai Inscription No.45. If these references refer to the same individual, they may suggest that political transformations on the Malay Peninsula in this transitional era were closely linked to power dynamics in the upper peninsula and the Chao Phraya basin since this stage.

Such connections align with Chinese records noting increased activity of groups identified as “Xian” in the peninsula. This coincided with the distinct expansion into the Chao Phraya Basin of Theravada Buddhism from the Mahavihara school, which had spread from Sri Lanka to the Tambralinga since the 12th century.⁶

Reconsidering “Xian” (暹): State, People, and Representation in Chinese Sources

The term “Xian” (暹) first appears in Chinese sources as the designation of a polity or power grouping in the southern seas that Kublai Khan initially contemplated subduing by force. Shortly thereafter, the Yuan court adopted a diplomatic approach and sent the mission to Xian on 17 July 1282. (YS 12: 6b) Nevertheless, the first diplomatic mission from the ruler of Xian ‘State’ (暹國主) reached Guangdong on 26 November 1292 (YS 16: 13b). On 4 June 1293, the Yuan court dispatched envoys to recruit and persuade Xian again. Thereafter, on 5 July 1294, a ruler named “Gǎnmùdīng” (敢木丁)⁷, from “Bìchábùlǐchéng” (必察不里城, Phetchaburi city), dispatched tribute envoys to the Yuan court. On 18 August 1294 (YS 18: 4b), the Yuan authorities recorded an order requiring “Gǎnmùdīng” (敢木丁) the ‘King’ of the ‘State’ of Xian (暹國王) to appear at court (YS 18: 7a). These notices suggest that the

⁵ This name persisted in the nomenclature of the rulers of Sukhothai city well into the early 16th century, appearing as 'Sri Sairon-narong Songkhram' (ศรีไสยรณรงค์สงคราม) in the Nai Si Yotha Ok Buat Inscription (1507 CE).

⁶ According to the Polonnaruwa Inscription, Ananda Thera was dispatched during Vikramabahu I's reign to establish the Sri Lankan Mahavihara Theravada in Tambralinga. See Winai (2543: 73).

⁷ Derived from Kamrateñ, a high-ranking honorific title in the ancient Angkorian socio-political hierarchy.

Chinese acknowledged 'Xian' as a State (國) under a King (國王), distinct from a city (城, Chéng) like Phetchaburi.⁸ This recognition was a prerequisite for Xian's formal integration into the Yuan tributary framework.

Modern interpretations⁹ have often relied on passages from the *Dade Nanhai zhi* (大德南海志) (1304), especially the phrase "Xian State: control Shangshui [and] Sùgūdī (Sukhothai)." (暹國管上水速孤低) to argue that 'Xian' could not have referred to Sukhothai because the sources list the two separately. On this basis, some scholars equate Xian with Ayutthaya before the formal establishment of Ayutthaya in 1351. Such interpretations, however, tend to abstract isolated phrases from their documentary context and insufficiently correlate them with contemporaneous evidence.

Three principal methodological issues arise:

First, interpreting "Xian Guo" (暹國) as strictly equivalent to a single urban center—such as Sukhothai, Ayutthaya, or Suphanburi—is problematic. In Yuan and early Ming sources, Guo (國) functioned as a diplomatic-political designation rather than a territorially fixed state in the modern sense. It was not always derived from the name of a specific capital. The designation "Zhao-wa Guo" (爪哇國), for instance, referred broadly to a recognized political entity rather than to a single urban center (see Wade 2005, s.v. "Java"; Kelley 2023: 57). Similarly, Xian should be understood as a political entity within the Chinese tributary framework rather than a fixed urban coordinate.

Second, the era spanning the end of the 13th century and the eve of the Dade reign is a particularly problematic period regarding evidentiary consistency. While local epigraphic records of the Siamese polities—most notably the Sukhothai inscriptions—abruptly halt in 1292¹⁰ Chinese sources report a flurry of movements that only further obscure the historical narrative of the time. Notably, the *Yuan shi* record separate tribute missions from Sukhothai (速古臺) originating from the 'southern seas' (海南) on 15 June 1299 (YS 20: 4a), a four months after an embassy from the Barbarian of Xian (Xianfan/暹番) and its heir (世子) had arrived in China and received an imperial tiger seal from the Yuan court on 2 February 1299 (YS 20: 1a). During this same interval, the *Dade Nanhai zhi* explicitly identifies the state of 'Xian' as 'governing' (Guan) both Sukhothai and Shangshui. Such assertions necessitate an exceptional degree of caution in evidentiary interpretation.

Furthermore, the toponym Shangshui (上水) should not be read literally as "up-river" but as a proper place name. Ming-period geographical descriptions, such as *Yingya Shenglan* (1451)

⁸ Regardless of whether the leadership may overlap with the same name within a close timeframe; notably, 'Gǎnmùdīng' of Phetchaburi and the King of Xian appear just two pages apart within the same fascicle (juan 18) of YS. which could be the same person in different contexts, or entirely different individuals.

⁹ Advanced by Yamamoto Tatsuro (1989: 51), Ishii Yoneo (2004: 38), and Chris Baker (2003: 44-45)

¹⁰ The latest years' records in Ramkhamheang and the 13th-century Sukhothai inscriptions.

of Ma Huan descriptions situate Shangshui approximately 200 li (about 67 miles) northwest of the “country” (of Ayutthaya), noting that this city can access the back door of Yunnan.¹¹

Third, the retroactive identification of pre-1351 Ayutthaya with the state of 'Xian' risks overlooking crucial contextual evidence. This identification contradicts Chinese records indicating that 'Xian'—if equated with Ayutthaya—was subordinate to 'Luohu' (Lavo) in 1349 (DYZL: 11b). Such a premise would imply that the pre-1349 administration in Ayutthaya was a political faction entirely distinct from that of King Ramathibodi I, the kingdom's recognized founder. It would further necessitate that this preceding group was subsequently displaced or forced to relinquish control of 'Ayutthaya' or 'Xian' to facilitate his accession—a complication that renders a straightforward identification of Ayutthaya with Xian increasingly problematic.

To clarify these issues, it is necessary to distinguish between two distinct but overlapping usages in Chinese sources:

1. Xian as a polity (暹國).

In this sense, Xian denoted a sphere of authority that may or may not have possessed a capital explicitly named 'Xian.' Core territories can be tentatively located in the Upper Chao Phraya basin. The two cities attributed to Xian in Chinese sources—Sukhothai and Shangshui—can both be geographically situated within this region. At certain moments, this sphere of authority may have extended to selected peninsular port polities along trans-peninsular trade routes.

2. Xian as a people (暹人).

As an ethnonym, Xian referred to a widely dispersed population not confined to a single political unit. Zhou Daguan records that groups identified as Xian resided in Angkor shortly before 1297, engaging in silk production, while others were involved in frontier conflicts in the Chenla (Angkor) border. From the *Yuan shi* to the accounts *Daoyi Zhilüe* (1349) of Chinese traveller Wang Dayuan, references indicate that Xian people (暹人) had long engaged in warfare with Malay communities before the year 1295 and launched attacks reaching as far as the Dānmaxī (單馬錫) before 1349. These notices demonstrate the high mobility and military dynamism of Xian populations during the 13th and 14th centuries. Ethnic designation did not necessarily correspond to fixed state boundaries or centers.

In the historiographical tradition and perspective of Lanna, 'Siam' was identified as the kingdom centered within the Upper Basin.

The *Jinakālamālī* explicitly records the Pali phrase “Syāmadese, Sukhodhayapure” (In the Syām Region, in the city of Sukhothai),¹² identifying the primary cities within this network

¹¹ (“國之西北去二百餘里有一市鎮名上水可通雲南後門”) *Yingya Shenglan*: 16a.

¹² Appears in passage like “สยามเทศ สุโขทัยปุเร ธัมมราชา นาม ราชา รัชชั กาลเสีฯ”. (JKM: 122)

as Sukhodhaya (Sukhothai), Sajjanalaya (Si Satchanalai), Jayanada (modern-day Phitsanulok), and Vajirapagara (modern-day Kamphaeng Phet).¹³

Conversely, when referring to Ayutthaya, the text distinctly employs the term “Kamphojarattha, Ayojjhapura” (In the Kamphoja state, in the city of Ayojjha).¹⁴ This identifies Ayodhya (an early Ayutthaya official named before the 17th century)¹⁵ as part of the Kamphoja state¹⁶—a political entity previously centered at Lavo during the conflicts with Haripuñjaya in the Chronicles stories. The core cities mentioned in this network include Ayojjhapura (Ayodhya), Suvannabhumi (Suphanburi), and Kamphoja (Lavo).

In summary, the perspective of the Lanna people, at least by the early 16th century, bifurcated the city-state networks of the Chao Phraya Basin into two distinct regional blocs: the Upper region designated as Syāmalesa, centered around Sukhothai, Si Satchanalai, and Jayanada (Song Khwae); and the Lower region designated as Kamphojarattha, comprising Ayodhya, Suvannabhumi, and Lavo as its primary centers.

Geographical Representation of ‘Xian’ and ‘Luohu’ in Chinese Records

According to the *Yuan Shi*, Volume 209 (Foreign States II - Annam), the Right Chancellor of the Province (行省右丞), Sügetü (唆都), stated:

“Jiaozhi (Annam) shares borders with the various states of Chenla, Champa, Yunnan, Xian, and Myanmar...”¹⁷

This passage indicates that Jiaozhi shared a common frontier with 'Xian'.

According to Wang Dayuan, a fundamental contrast existed between the two domains: the land of Xian (Siam) was characterized by its barrenness, whereas Luohu (Lavo) was renowned for its fertility.

Despite Chris Baker’s attempt to explain the 'barren' of Xian (identified in his theory as Ayutthaya) by hypothesizing that the lower Chao Phraya delta was marshy and saline, while citing Ma Huan’s records (Baker 2003: 47), which are similar to the description of Xian in

¹³ These cities were listed as those whose people assembled to celebrate the King of Sukhothai’s construction of the stupa and the vihara at Satchanalai. (JKM: 128)

¹⁴ Appears in passage like “กัมโพชรัฐสุส เจว อโยชขปรัสส จ อีสสร”. (JKM: 129)

¹⁵ This traditional name last appears in Phra That Si Song Rak inscription (1563) as พระนครศรีอโยธยา; Henceforth, the term ‘Ayodhya’ will be employed, in accordance with primary sources.

¹⁶ The polity of Lavo. In the *Jinakālamāli*, the names Lavo (Lavapura) and Kamphoja are used interchangeably within the same chapter, yet both denote the same geopolitical entity. See (JKM: 110-111)

¹⁷ (“交趾與占臘占城雲南暹緬諸國接壤...”) YS 209: 10a.

Daoyi Zhilüe word-for-word.¹⁸ However, it is difficult to deny that Ayutthaya and its surroundings were naturally vast floodplains. As Charnvit (2523) notes, this exceptional fertility enabled large-scale rice production, providing the essential foundation for the rise of the Ayutthaya. Furthermore, records from another Zheng He scribe—specifically Fei Xin, who visited Ayodhya since the third voyage—describe Xianluo (Ayodhya) as having “The fields are level and fertile, the grain is mostly abundant and ripe”.¹⁹ His poetry further notes that “rice crops flourish through the summer”.²⁰ Such portrayals directly contradict the definition of Xian's territory as a barren or mountainous landscape.

Such descriptions may correspond more closely to the situations of the Upper Basin, which lies below the mountainous regions. The city of Sukhothai itself is located in a dry area (Srisakra 1999: 7-9) and necessitated a sophisticated irrigation system to divert and store water for urban use (Nikom 2000: 56-57). In contrast, the Chao Phraya Valley was defined by a large fertile lowland suitable for rice cultivation that could feed large numbers of people. (Srisakra 1986)

In the *Dade Nanhai zhi*, the Cities under Xian's jurisdiction included Sukhothai and Shangshui. Notably, Sukhothai was categorized alongside Shangshui, which Ma Huan later identified as a Shizhen (市鎮)—a strategic market town or commercial hub. Which is located in the upper reach of the country of Xianluo (Ayodhya).

By the mid-Ming Dynasty, geographical treatises such as Zhang Huang's *Tushu Bian* (1613) began correlating cardinal directions with specific topographies: “this land's, the southeast was fertile and productive, while the northwest was mountainous.”²¹ This observation reached its definitive form in mid-Qing Dynasty documents. The *Huangchao Wenxian Tongkao* (1785) states: “The northwest consists of rugged and barren soil, which is the land of Xian; the southeast consists of level, expansive, and fertile terrain, which is the land of Luohu.”²² These records explicitly link geographical sterility with the Northern domain (Xian) and the abundance of rice production with the Southeastern lowlands (Luohu).

Ultimately, the Late-Qing dynasty map [Map 2] delineates the historical regions of Xian (暹) and Luohu (羅斛). It situates Xian in the upper reaches of the Menam River (湄南河), whereas Luohu is positioned downstream, close to the river mouth (湄南河口) and the coastal regions of the Gulf of Thailand.

¹⁸ The only modifications involve replacing the phrase “Deep secluded mountain ranges in the hinterland” (內嶺深邃) from the DYZL with “The interior land is damp and humid” (內地潮濕), while omitting the section stating that “the grain supply relied annually on Lavo” (穀米歲仰羅斛).

¹⁹ (Mills & Ptak 1996: 42), (“田平而沃，稼多豐熟”) XCSL: 4a.

²⁰ (“九夏稻禾榮”) XCSL: 4a. Translated by the author.

²¹ (“其土地東南平衍饒稻西北多大山”) *Tushu Bian* 51: 16b. Translated by the Author.

²² (“西北土礪确暹地也東南土平衍羅斛地也”) *Huangchao Wenxian Tongkao* 297:1b Translated by the Author.

Taken together, these records suggest a relatively consistent geographical perception—whether from neighboring regions like Lanna or from maritime sources in Chinese Ming and Qing Dynasty archives—have consistently held a similar understanding from at least the 16th to 19th centuries regarding the core area of “Polity” or “Place” known as “Syām/Xian.” Both sources apparently place it within the Inland-Upper Basin.

Map 2: Map of countries in the Southern Sea’s shores 南洋濱海各國圖 (*Nanyang binhai geguo tu*) from Xu Jiyu’s *Ying Huan Zhi Lue* (1848) © LOC/Annotations by the Author

- A: Xian (Siam)
- B: Luohu (Lavo)
- C: Menam (Chao Phraya) River
- D: Bangkok, the capital
- E: Menam (Chao Phraya) River mouth

An illustrative episode concerns the polity referred to in the *Jinakālamālī* as ‘Kamphoja,’ which could correspond to the Luo-hu (羅斛). According to the chronicle, this power

exploited the prevailing “famine”²³ shortage within the Jayanada city (ชยนาทปุระ) to seize control over it. This city is a significant strategic node within the riverine transport network over the Upper Basin of the ‘Syāmadesa’, which could correspond to the Xian (遷). As a result, King Lithai (Mahathammaracha I) of Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai was compelled to offer tribute to King Ramathibodi of Ayodhya to secure the city’s return. This episode aligns chronologically with Wang Dayuan’s report that “Xian submitted to Luohu in May 1349”. Furthermore, the underlying cause of this event aligns with the geographical conditions of Xian, as Wang Dayuan states: “The soil is barren and unsuitable for cultivation; thus, for the grain supply relied annually on Luohu.”

In summary, the evidence suggests that both “Xian” as a polity and “Xian” as people were historically fluid categories.²⁵ Political authority was negotiated and layered; ethnic identity was mobile and not territorially confined.

From Mobility to Political Identity: The Functional Emergence of “Siam”

The initial expansion of the Siamese group was characterized by a distinct social structure, particularly regarding the customary regulations governing the management of resources, manpower, and inheritance. The Sukhothai polity serves as a primary case study; as Baker & Pasuk (2017) note, the societies maintained a strong warrior character, therefore necessitating systematic protocols for distributing spoils of war. Epigraphic evidence from the Ram Khamhaeng and Wat Si Chum inscriptions suggests a hierarchical redistribution model: captured assets were first tendered to the King, Lord, or elders.²⁶ Subsequently, these superiors would reallocate the resources²⁷ among subordinates based on seniority.²⁸ This structure may be conceptualized as a hierarchical redistribution network, as [Figure 1].

²³ (เอกทา กิร ชยนาทปุรัมหิ ทุพภิกขภย ชาตฯ อโยชชราชา รามาทิปติ กัมโพชโต อาคันตวา ธัญญวิกกยเลเสน ตั คัณหิฯ “Once, during a famine in Jayanada, King Ramadhipati of Ayodhya arrived from Kamphoja and seized the city under the pretext of selling grain.”) translated by the Author. (JKM: 129)

²⁴ (“土瘠不宜耕種穀米歲仰羅斛”) DYZL: 12b

²⁵ Regarding the fluid nature of the ‘Xian’ (Siam), a conceptual analysis from a historical-geographical perspective can be found in Wansa (2025).

²⁶ A similar pattern of spoils tendering appears in both inscriptions. In the case of Ramkhamhaeng, he defeats Khun Samchon and returns the spoils to his father. Similarly, Si Sattha defeats Khun Jang and delivers the spoils to King Loethai.

²⁷ In this sense, including the asset, person, and “city” or “polity”.

²⁸ The Wat Si Chum Inscription states that when King Si Naw Nam Thum acquired the spoils of war, he distributed them among his subordinates, giving two shares to the elder brother and one to the younger. (“พี่สองน้องได้หนึ่ง”)

Figure 1: A simplified model of hierarchical resource redistribution in early Siamese polities

The inheritance and succession patterns of 'father-to-son' and 'elder-to-younger brother' constituted fundamental norms documented in nearly every royal inscription of the Sukhothai. This hierarchical structure was not confined to the elite but was also disseminated among the commoners (Phrai) throughout the realm.²⁹ However, this seniority-based system of resource and power distribution inherently generated complications regarding legitimacy and charisma, which emerged as persistent variables undermining the unity of the early Siamese city-states.

In the case of Sukhothai, these structural tensions were evidenced by the fragmentation and declarations of independence by constituent city-states following the demise of a charismatic paramount leader. The emergence of competing power centers often occurred when legitimacy was contested among multiple claimants—for instance, when a deceased king's brother and his son both possessed significant charisma and administrative bases in different locales. This duality, or multiplicity, of power centers destabilized the network's cohesion, leading individual city-states to assert their own legitimacy.³⁰ Such precursors of instability were recurrent in early Siamese history.

A notable power vacuum occurred following the reign of King Loethai, which probably caused a temporary displacement of the ruling lineage. This was exemplified by Prince Lithai, who was initially relegated to ruling Si Satchanalai before eventually mobilizing forces to reclaim Sukhothai and reintegrate its network of city-states.³¹ However, the most decisive blow to Sukhothai's sovereignty was the internecine conflict between Phraya Ram of Sukhothai and Phraya Ban Mueang of Jayanada (Song Khwae)—half-brothers who both asserted independent legitimacy.

This internal fragmentation provided a strategic opening for King Intharacha of Ayodhya to intervene. By that period, Ayodhya—led by the Suphanburi faction—had accumulated substantial wealth by dominating maritime exports and formalizing tributary trade with the Ming Dynasty. Drawing from the lessons of his predecessor, Borommarachathirat I, who

²⁹ See Trongjai, ed.(2558: 195)

³⁰ A similar power multiplicity and destabilized circumstance also exist in the Early Ayodhya city-states. See Winai (2548: 116).

³¹ The crucial event was introduced in the Khmer version of the Pa Mamuang inscription.

faced persistent resistance from Sukhothai's martial defense, Intharacha eschewed total military conquest. Instead, he employed a sophisticated blend of mediation and matrimonial alliances (Intermarriage). Although the immediate conflict was settled through compromise due to the intervention of this third power, the structural outcome was the near-equalization of status among Sukhothai's primary city-states. This irreversible decentralization ultimately prevented Sukhothai from re-establishing a singular power center, leading to its gradual absorption into the Ayodhyan sphere of influence.

Nevertheless, this fragmentation and polycentricity were equally discernible within Ayodhya. Internal instability was manifest in several key successional disputes: the removal of Ramesuan from the Ayodhyan throne by his uncle, Borommarachathirat I of the Suphanburi—forcing Ramesuan back to his provincial stronghold of Lavo—as well as Intharacha's later deposition of Ramaracha. Perhaps most emblematic was the fatal struggle for the throne between the two royal brothers, Chao Ai Phraya of Suphanburi and Chao Yi Phraya of Phraek Si Racha.

Such confrontations may reflect a broader structural tendency within Tai city-state societies. Specifically, the recurring friction between competing power units based in 'Mueang Luk Luang' (Princely Cities) represents a distinctive characteristic of the Siamese polities in the Chao Phraya Basin. This system empowered provincial centers with sufficient autonomous resources and legitimacy to challenge the central authority, particularly during periods of leadership transition.³²

The Dual-Core Network: Inland-Hubs and Coastal Gateways

The early Siamese city-states maintained significant engagements in maritime trade and diplomacy, as evidenced by the high frequency and diligence of their tributary missions to the Yuan court.³³ These missions were dispatched either as collective entities representing regional networks—such as Xian or Lavo—or as individual units. Notably, the diplomatic outreach from the 'City' (城) of Phetchaburi in 1294 and Sukhothai in 1299. These city-states established contact with China via the South China Sea route, primarily through the port of Guangzhou in Guangdong province.

Archaeological evidence—specifically high-quality ceramics produced that were influenced by Chinese wares found extensively across the Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai network—demonstrates the commercial ties and sophisticated technological exchanges between the Upper basin and China. Consequently, the emergence or resurgence of port-cities around the Gulf can be viewed as inextricably linked to the dynamics of inland riverine networks and the expansion of Chinese maritime trade during this pre-modern era. Broadly speaking, the early Siamese 'mandala-like' polities within the Chao Phraya Basin and Gulf regions during the

³² See Winai (2548: 116)

³³ The embassy from Xian to the Yuan court was recorded 8 times, from Lavo 5 times, and once each from Phetchaburi city and Sukhothai, during the entire Yuan reign.

13th to 15th centuries can be categorized into two major groups based on their distinct characteristics and functional structures as follows:

1. The Hybrid Inland Hub Group

This group's power base was strategically situated at the nexus between trans-continental cart tracks through mountain passes and the headwaters of major riverine networks flowing toward the coast. Their primary function was to collect and redistribute maritime resources—such as cowrie shells from the Maldives, which served as regional currency—into deep hinterland regions like Lanna, Laos, and Yunnan. Conversely, they acted as intermediaries for inland resources, including forest products, minerals, and rare gemstones, channeling them toward coastal emporiums. Geographically, they functioned as a trading post between the Gulf of Martaban and the central Mekong River basin.

Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai polity, as the representative of this group, developed from the control of a critical logistics node in the upper basin, particularly around the city of Sukhothai in the late 12th to early 13th centuries. The strategic establishment of Sukhothai enabled control over valuable resources and facilitated trade and communication with other regions, as indicated by the Least Cost Path analysis (Singtuen et al. 2024: 1, 6). This was led by Tai Mueang-polity leaders named Si Naw Nam Thum from the Upper Chao Phraya region, and probably constantly led the community's networks that controlled the Pa Sak and Nan river basins.

A new perspective of interpretations from the Wat Si Chum Inscription suggests that the initial acquisition of this strategic city of Sukhothai and Mueang Haeng (Old Tak city) on the same occasion might have been not just from war but also through an “exchange” (Winai 2554: 42, 60) with a local leader named Yi(E) Daeng Phloeng (possibly of Mon ethnicity). These cities provided convenient access to western mountain passes via Tak and Mae Sot (probably related to Mueang Chot in the inscriptions), leading directly to the port-cities of the Gulf of Martaban. If these Tai groups could indeed secure such a vital stronghold through wealth rather than solid conquest, it may imply they had accumulated significant capital over at least several decades by controlling inland resource corridors.

Furthermore, the inscription reveals a kinship-based relationship with the ancient Khmer power of the Tonle Sap, which had exercised dominance over the Chao Phraya Basin since the late 10th century. This connection was likely maintained through frontier outposts in the Pasak Basin, providing a direct link to the ancient Angkorian 'Royal Road' (Rajamarga). A quintessential example is Mueang Rat, whose ruler, Pha Mueang³⁴—the son of Si Naw Nam Thum of Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai polity³⁵—entered into a matrimonial alliance with the daughter of the Angkorian king. Through this union, Pha Mueang was invested with political legitimacy and received strategic support from Angkor during the early 13th century.

Following the decline of Angkorian influence in the central plains, a decisive conflict emerged between the rising Tai power and the remaining proxies of Angkor (or perhaps the

³⁴ The Wat Si Chum inscription portrays him as a figure who 'commanded a numerous man, elephants and amassed vast territories,' (คุมลงแสนช้างมาฟากรอม บ้านเมืองออกหลวงหลายแควม) signifying his extensive control over military manpower (elephants), labor, and numerous subordinate polities (Mueang)

³⁵ In which the inscription states that Si Naw Nam Thum is sovereign in two “Nakhon”(cities), one is Sukhothai, and the other is Si Satchanalai. These dual cities roles as the core of the city-states network.

autonomous local authorities). This struggle culminated in the Battle for Sukhothai city that occurred around the mid-13th century, resulting in a victory for the Tai Mueang's confederation of the Mueang Rat and Mueang Bang Yang. This event appears to mark a major decline in Bayon-style Angkorian administrative influence in the region.

In the aftermath of this confrontation, archaeological and historical evidence reveal a restructuring and expansion of city-states along newly established trade and communication routes. This new order adopted the "Mueang" administrative model characteristic of Tai traditions, superseding the former Dvaravati-Angkorian frameworks. This transition laid the foundation for the Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai power network, organized around four strategic nodes (quadrants) that functioned as the network's commercial hubs, power bases, and state frontiers (Raṭṭhasīmā):

Table 1: Strategic Quadrant-Based Nodes within the Inland-Hubs Networks.

Quadrant	Major Cities / Nodes	Strategic Role
North	Thung Yang (in modern-day Uttaradit)	Functioned as an inland redistribution hub channeling hinterland resources into the Chao Phraya Basin.
East	Song Khwae (Jayanada / modern-day Phitsanulok)	Controlled Nan River transport and eastern overland access toward the Pasak Basin and Middle Mekong region.
West	Tak and Haeng, Chakangraw and Nakhon Chum (modern-day Kamphaeng Phet)	Controlled overland routes via Mae Sot (Mueang Chot) toward the Gulf of Martaban and riverine transport along the Ping River.
South	Phra Bang (modern-day Nakhon Sawan)	Major riverine gateway and transshipment hub connecting the Upper Basin to maritime routes via the Tha Chin and Lower Chao Phraya rivers.

These nodes collectively constituted the strategic infrastructure of the Si Satchanalai-Sukhothai network, an entity generally referred to as the "Northern Cities" (Mueang Nuea) from the perspective of the Lower Basin.

2. The Coastal and Delta Port-Polities Group

The primary settlements of this group were situated at the river mouths encircling the Gulf of Thailand—a region characterized by intense maritime cultural exchange since at least the 6th century. This area exhibits a complex stratigraphy of shifting and overlapping civilizations, beginning with early Indianized polities such as Dvaravati, followed by the later expansion of influence from Angkor.

However, many Dvaravati coastal centers were abandoned or relocated long before the 10th century, due to coastal progradation (the receding coastline) and the shifting of major river distributaries.³⁶ Only a few inland nodes remained continuously inhabited or were later revitalized, such as Lavo and parts of Si Thep until the early 13th century.³⁷ These served as strategic bases for the Angkor to consolidate resources from the Chao Phraya basin, reaching a zenith during the Bayon period under Jayavarman VII. During this era, Angkorian authority extended deep into the plains, constructing new cities and religious monuments—such as Kosinarai city on the Mae Klong River or Prasat Mueang Sing on the Khwea Noi River—and others on the foundations of old Dvaravati sites.

Following the waning of Angkorian authority in the mid-to-late 13th century, these Bayon-style centers were either modified or abandoned. This decline coincided with a significant surge of migration and goods from the hinterlands toward the coast, driven by a growing demand for local forest products and the maritime commercial expansion of Chinese and Muslim merchant networks. This economic shift catalyzed the emergence or resurgence of new port-polities in the Lower basin.

Initially, these nodes were concentrated on the western side of the delta along the riverine network, including Phraek (in modern-day Sangklaburi, Chainat province), Suphanburi, Ratchaburi, and Phetchaburi. These revitalized cities maintained logistical links with inland networks and were occasionally integrated into larger confederations, such as during the Sukhothai supremacy under King Ram Khamhaeng. Contemporary and later records—including the Ram Khamhaeng Inscription, Lanna, and Mon chronicles like the *Razadarit Ayedawbon*—consistently attest to the expansive reach of his authority over these riverine and coastal cities.

Notably, the rise of these Chao Phraya basin communities occurred alongside the spread of Lankan Theravada Buddhism, probably from Nakhon Si Thammarat. This religious shift profoundly impacted the cosmological layout of Siamese cities. The ‘Phra Mahathat’ (Great Reliquary Stupa) replaced the Khmer-Bayon stone Prasat or Vihara (temples) as the community center. Existing stone temples were often modified, with their towers extended into a unique tall Prang or stupas, a transition evident from the 13th Century onward.

After the reign of King Ram Khamhaeng, these lower basin polities likely began organizing their power structures into a ‘Mueang’ network system. Initially fragmented among autonomous centers such as Lavo, Suphanburi, and Phetchaburi, a definitive new center emerged in the early 14th Century at the Chao Phraya delta confluence.³⁸ and the river bend mound from the east riverbank near the present-day Wat Phanan Choeng, or the area named

³⁶ In the case of Ancient Nakhon Pathom, see Saritpong (2557: 197).

³⁷ See Suriya (2019: 117-132)

³⁸ The vicinity area is known as ‘Nong Sano’ (หนองสน, “Sesbania Swamp”). Early Portuguese and Persian sources render the name of Ayodhya as “Sarnao” or “Shahr-i-naur,” possibly reflecting older phonetic forms. See also Winai, ed. (2559: 50)

‘Samphao Lom’ (Capsized Junk), was situated roughly 60 miles from the modern-day coastline. It represented the furthest inland point navigable by large ocean-going junks before the river meandered westward and narrowed. Functioning as a prime transshipment hub for Chinese and Muslim maritime traders, its strategic significance was consecrated in 1325 by the establishment of a colossal Buddha image, ‘Phra Phuttha Chao Phanaeng Choeng,’³⁹ which served as a monumental landmark.

Subsequently, a moat was excavated to link the Lop Buri River with the Chao Phraya at the bend fronting Wat Phanan Choeng, transforming the interior into a fortified island. On this site, a new capital was formally established in 1351. The expansive network of this Ayodhya-centered polity is documented in the Laws on Abduction (Laksana Lak-pha), dated 1356, promulgated by King Ramathibodi I (KTSD 3: 1). The decree delineates the constituent cities of the network, tracing a maritime-to-riverine corridor from the Gulf northward as follows:

⁴⁰**Table 2:** Principal Strategic Nodes of the Coastal and Delta Port-Polities Network

Principal Nodes/Cities	Strategic Role
1. Phetchaburi	A major port-polity on the upper Gulf of Thailand, serving as the gateway for trans-isthmus routes toward the Andaman port of Tanintharyi (Tenasserim or Tanawrsri).
2. Ratchaburi	A historic hub of exchange between the upper Gulf and inland riverine networks since the 6th century, exercising control over the Mae Klong river delta.
3. Suphanburi	Situated in the heart of the Tha Chin River Basin, it dominated a vast and highly productive rice-growing plain.
4. Sa-phong-khlong	An ancient city and critical node along the Chao Phraya riverine network during the mid-14th century, also appears in Sukhothai’s inscription No.11 as ‘Kampong Khlong’, likely situated in the vicinity of modern-day Singburi.
5. Phlap Phraek Si Rachathirat (Phraek Si Racha)	A major princely city of Suphanburi and early Ayodhya, located on the Noi River at the strategic divergence of the Chao Phraya flowing from the north and the Tha Chin from the west (in modern-day Chainat).
6. Nakhon Phrom (Lavo)	Likely a scribal error for Nakhon Phra Ram (‘City of Prince Rama’), a Thai honorific for Lavo or Lop Buri. It was a major center before Ayodhya in the lower Chao Phraya Basin Polities and the main princely city of early Ayodhya.

These nodes defined the Raṭṭhamaṇḍala (the territorial sphere of power)⁴¹ of the early Siamese City-states.

Simultaneously, these locations served as pivotal strategic nodes, integrating resources and populations through trade and transit across an expansive intra-regional logistics network. Spanning from the ‘gateways to interior resources’ to the ‘portals of maritime commerce,’ these nodes constituted the essential foundation that propelled the commercial economy and

³⁹ The first event that was recorded in the Luang Prasoet Chronicle of Ayutthaya.

⁴⁰ The name ‘Nakhon Phrom’ survives in the titles of later governors of Lop Buri as Ok-Phra Nakhon Phram. (KTSD 1: 323)

⁴¹ The words that are used in the Wat Asokaram Inscription of Sukhothai, as well as the word Raṭṭhasīmā to define the sphere of authority of the polity networks.

the state architecture of Ayodhya (Xianluo) and later Ayutthaya—a polity ultimately forged through the consolidation of these interconnected city-state networks.

Dynamic and the Claiming of Unification

The power structure governing the logistics networks of the Chao Phraya River basin and the Gulf of Thailand underwent a significant paradigm shift beginning in May 1349. Chinese records underscore this transition, recording the emergence of a new regional authority resulting from the purported ‘unification’ of the Xian (Siam) state by the state of Luohu (Lavo). This geopolitical integration established a new entity within the Oriental worldview known as Xian-Luohu. Conversely, local chronicles suggest that the formal inauguration of the new metropolis, ‘Si Ayodhya’, occurred two years later in March 1351.

The singular event corroborating the Chinese records regarding Xian’s ‘submission’ to the Lavo-based power is found in the *Jinakālamālī*. This Lanna religious chronicle details the seizure of Jayanada (Song Khwae/Phitsanulok) in the Syāmalesa by King Ramathibodi of Ayojjapura from Kamphojarattha (Lavo state), capitalizing on a period of scarcity of rice that plagued the city, executed by the Techawatti (Borommachathirat I) of Suvarnabhumi (Suphanburi). This military campaign compelled King Lithai to ‘tribute’ in exchange for the city’s return—an act that aligns precisely with the Chinese accounts of Xian’s subordination to Luohu. This narrative is further supported by King Lithai’s own inscriptions, which state that he resided in Song Khwae for seven years to restore the city’s Great Relic (Mahathat) and pacify the eastern territories.⁴²

Nonetheless, it appears that the Lavo state leveraged this ‘submission’ as a claim of total unification in its diplomatic engagements with China, effectively eclipsing and terminating the independent maritime trade and diplomatic role of the former Xian state. The establishment of a new capital at the northernmost navigable point for maritime junks within the delta represented an important consolidation of physical power over the Chao Phraya riverine network. Although a period of relative territorial stability followed between King Ramathibodi and King Lithai, the Ayodhya (former Lavo state) subsequently embarked on an assertive process of inland expansion and political intervention. This trajectory is characteristic of an emergent port-polity, driven by the necessity to control inland resources for export and, crucially, to dominate the pre-existing interior logistics networks.

What distinguished Ayodhya (and later Ayutthaya) from other island-based coastal states of the same era was its large hinterland (Baker 2003: 62). This was the strategic outcome of a state formation that integrated a network of pre-existing inland hubs—notably the former Sukhothai state known as Northern city-states—with the coastal or estuarine port-polities that formed Ayodhya’s primary power base. Through this integration, these former inland centers were effectively transformed into an expansive hinterland.

Ultimately, Ayodhya successfully established its hegemony as the center for resource consolidation and the export monopoly of the Chao Phraya basin. This dominance was anchored by its control over the outflow of indigenous products to China and high-quality

⁴² See the Khao Sumanakut Inscription in Trongjai, ed. (2558: 246)

Sangkhalok ceramics to the Southeast Asian Archipelago and Ryukyu. The primary catalyst for this economic ascendancy was Ayodhya's strategic integration into the Ming Dynasty's tributary system. During an era of Chinese maritime prohibition (Haijin), this trade relationship generated immense profits and cemented Ayodhya's status as a vital commercial entrepôt, where international merchants were compelled to converge for access to the restricted Chinese market.

Conclusion

The inscriptions and lawsuit records of Early Siamese were abundant with trade-related information, including details about goods, animals, and persons (slaves) exchanges as well as pilgrim stories. These elements synchronized and may have relied on the expansion of commercial trends within Southeast Asia. In conclusion, early "Siam" was a fluid, decentralized social entity, beyond modern historiography's definitions. This article highlights gaps in the records, emphasizing that analyzing Chinese sources requires focusing on suffixes like Chèng (城), Guo (國), Bang (邦), Fan (番), Guozhu (國主), Wang (王), and Shizi (世子), which will become more complex and layered in the diplomatic relations of early Xianluo (Ayodhya)-Ming Dynasty courts. These distinctions reshape the socio-political context of these entities and could enhance our understanding of socio-economic changes in Southeast Asia during the transition from the Early Age of Commerce to the Age of Commerce.

While the Siamese state remained politically decentralized—relying heavily on inter-dynastic negotiations and the negotiated autonomy of provincial lords—this systematic network served as a robust foundation. It effectively funneled wealth from trans-peninsular trade routes into a centralized structure, paving the way for a maritime power.

By the late 16th century, under the Sukhothai Dynasty (House of Phra Ruang), following the decline of Toungoo hegemony, Ayutthaya began a rigorous process of centralization. This era marked a significant shift in power and wealth from traditional lineage-based provincial lords toward a centralized bureaucracy comprised of both local and foreign officials. This transition was further catalyzed by the arrival of Western East India companies and the rise of new export markets, most notably Japan, which momentarily rivaled China's economic influence over the Ayutthayan court. The complex dynamics and catalysts that propelled Ayutthaya—the ultimate culmination of Siamese socio-political development—to its zenith in the global maritime theater during the latter half of the 17th century remain a compelling subject for further scholarly investigation.

Abbreviations

- DYZL – *Daoyi Zhilüe* 島夷志略 [Brief Account of the Islands Barbarians].
- JKM – *Jinakālmālīnī phāsā makhot* ชินกาลมาลีนี ภาษามคร [Jinakālamālī Pali text].
- KTSD – *Kotmai Tra Sam Duang* กฎหมายตราสามดวง [Laws of the Three Seals].
- TMNST – *Tamnan Mueang Nakhon Si Thammarat* ตำนานเมืองนครศรีธรรมราช [Chronicle of Nakhon Si Thammarat].

- XCSL – *Xingcha Shenglan* 星槎勝覽 [The Overall Survey of the Starry Galleon].
- YS – *Yuan Shi* 元史 [History of the Yuan].

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